

Innovative processing technologies for bio-based foamed thermoplastics

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Manufacturing technologies for bio-based materials

D8.3 Ethics Plan

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	description
b-bTPs	bio-based thermoplastics
BP	Business Plan
BM	Business Model
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
FIM	Foam Injection Moulding
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
GA	Grant Agreement
GenA	General Assembly
EAB	External Advisory Board
EAd	Ethics Advisor
EC	European Commission
ESLM	External Stakeholder Liaison Manager
HE	Horizon Europe
IM	Innovation Manager
PDEC	Place for Dissemination and Exploitation
PO	Project Officer
PQMP	Project Quality Management Plan
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the ethics procedures and describes the ethics plan created for the VITAL project. The beneficiaries of VITAL Consortium confirm compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law in the implementation of research activities not originally envisaged (or not described earlier) in the research plan will be ensured. The Consortium also confirms that any ethical concerns raised by those activities will be handled following rigorously the recommendations provided in the European Commission Ethics Self-Assessment Guidelines.

Ethical issues are handled in WP8 Management in Task 8.3 Ethics management (M1-M36, led by VTT). VITAL is compliant with EU, international and national ethics requirements and legislation and ensures that the provisions on ethics regulation and rules are implemented into all project activities. Ethical aspects will be considered by all consortium participants and monitored by VTT. This includes assessing and monitoring activities based on possible effects on the environment, safety especially in the laboratories and research facilities, public engagement, gender issues, cooperation with other scientific communities, data handling, storage and management, and innovation and ethical management.

Having considered the ethical issues around the project the consortium believes the ethical considerations associated with VITAL will be in relation to the following key items:

- a) Non-EU Countries - plan to export and import material between non-EU countries and the EU
- b) Artificial Intelligence

The consortium will ensure that all of these issues and any additional ethics issues that may emerge in the course of the project are carefully analysed and managed.

2. Introduction

The overall aim of VITAL is to develop **innovative processing solutions for foamed bio-based Thermoplastics** (b-bTPs), based on three processing value chains that cover the requirements for commercial scale processing in terms of: volume, size, materials, functionality and application. These processes will include:

1. Modification of high-volume production processes that are already highly controlled and automated:
 - a. **Foam Injection Moulding** (FIM) with AI-based process control of instrumented equipment allowing for tight control of critical parameters such as temperature, speed and residence times to ensure part conformity.
 - b. **Bead foaming** of b-bTPs combined with radio-frequency (steam-free) heating.
2. Globally-unique **3D b-bTPs foam printing** for mould-free, additive manufacture for rapid prototyping and bespoke production and massively reduce lead time and costs. The challenges and risks are much higher for the 3D printing approach, but the technical and commercial impacts much greater, being a disruptive technology.

Each of these will be realised using optimised formulations of existing and cutting-edge b-bTPs and additives. VITAL will create a globally unique database of foamed b-bTPs properties, that will be critical for further commercial exploitation beyond the project as plug-in data for commercial software such as Moldflow or Moldex3D for injection moulding simulation/optimisation and Abaqus for Finite

Element Analysis (FEA) for engineering design of new products/structures. This will enable:

- Mould modelling and design – Pre-process optimisation.

- Process modelling – Pre-process parameter setting to obtain the “best starting point”.
- More accurate modelling and actual in-process control.
- Modelling of final properties (FEA).

In addition, VITAL will achieve commercially viable closed loop, mechanical recycling taking into consideration the specific requirements for b-bTPs.

The VITAL project is a three-year project, which is divided into eight Work Packages (WPs) as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Work packages and their interactions in VITAL project (VITAL Methodology showing objectives and outputs).

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Good ethical principles are considered by all consortium partners in all their activities with the support of the project coordinator as part of WP8 coordination and management activities. The project coordinator also monitors the implementation of these ethical guidelines, and any significant issues or deviations will be reported to the VITAL General Assembly. There will be an expert to act as Ethics

Advisor (EAd), who will monitor the ethical issues involved and how they are handled. The EAd will attend project meetings when necessary and will be consulted on all ethical issues.

During the proposal preparation phase, having considered the ethical issues around the project the consortium believes the ethical considerations associated with VITAL will be in relation to the following key items:

- a) Non-EU Countries - plan to export and import material between non-EU countries and the EU
- b) Artificial Intelligence

This deliverable has a relationship to other activities (or deliverables) in the project that should be considered along with this document for further understanding of its contents (Table 1).

Table 1. Relation to other activities in the project.

Deliverable no.	Contributions
D7.2	This deliverable explains the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication activities
D7.4	This deliverable explains the gender equality plan
D7.5	This deliverable explains the data management plan (DMP)
D8.1	This deliverable explains PQMP procedures for communication, progress monitoring, quality assurance and risk management
D8.2	This deliverable explains detailed implementation plan for months 1-18

3. Ethical issues of VITAL project

Ethical issues are handled in WP8 Management in Task 8.3 Ethics management (M1-M36, led by VTT). Ethical aspects will be considered by all consortium participants and supported by VTT. This includes assessing and monitoring activities based on possible effects on the environment, safety especially in the laboratories and research facilities, public engagement, gender issues, cooperation with other scientific communities, data handling, storage and management, and innovation and ethical management.

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3.1 Non-EU Countries

Non-EU Countries – participation of Non-EU countries and plan to export and import material between non-EU countries and the EU.

VITAL has 3 Turkish partners (ARC, FAR, TOF). These 3 industrial partners will be supporting the outcomes of the project by completing necessary activities relating to part design and validation of new production processes. VITAL has 2 UK partners (FLO and IIL). FLO will be responsible for the formulation of flame-retardant grades of PLA that will be required for the industrial use cases. IIL will be leading the innovation management activities and will support all partners in establishing robust exploitation strategies. All project activities undertaken in these Non-EU countries are all activities that would all be acceptable activities within any EU country and under EU law. FLO(UK) will be supplying PLA as required for the end users and applications for the 3 value chains to EU partners as PIEP (PT), VTT (FI) and FHG (DE). These PLA materials will also be supplied to the industrial partners as appropriate and as required (ARC, TOF, ARC). AVI (DE) will supply FLO (UK) with appropriate additives for the relevant formulation of tailored grades. ARC, TOF, and FAR (TR) will receive materials from the EU partner to complete production trials and product validations.

For all import(s) and export(s) between EU > Non-EU and Non-EU > EU will follow all required protocols make available any and all information that will be deemed necessary to complete the import and/or export of the materials. For the avoidance of doubt, the materials referred to here, and in the proposal, activities refer only to materials that are required for industrial production – polymers and additives. These materials will be materials that are conventionally imported and exported between these countries already. The following non-exhaustive information (as appropriate and required) will be considered for all imports/exports:

- Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS) to specify the customs tariff number according to the content information
- Certificate of origin (CO) document
- Invoice (with the presence of ‘free of charge’ & ‘sample’ label and real price values of the materials on it, e.g. for catalysts, as appropriate)
- Declaration of Conformity - CE Marking
- Customs Tariff No supplied by the exporter with the purpose of use, working area of the goods
- Pictures of the goods taken and supplied by the exporter
- Export Request Forms will include: recipient’s name, the purpose of export, charge status, recipient’s address, recipient’s telephone, recipient’s e-mail, country of destination, the origin of country, gross and net weight of the material, package number, package type, package visuals, package dimensions, the responsibility of the cost for transfer and insurance, the responsibility of the cost for customs, expected time for delivery, shipper information if the recipient/importer is in charge of transfer and insurance.

All materials and chemicals that will be used within VITAL and/or imported or exported are intended to be non-toxic. In any case, occupational health and safety regulations will be adhered to for the handling of all materials and chemicals. All materials will be accompanied by the MSDS which will highlight the specific handling requirements.

3.2 Artificial Intelligence

VITAL will use artificial intelligence (AI) in order to establish a new method of smarter-materials processing to achieve better industrial production outcomes and ultimately result in better material performance. The AI will be applied to identify the patterns between processing parameters such as speed, temperature and pressure and the formation of cell structures during the polymer foaming process. The AI will be trained purely using industrial processing data gathering via sensed production equipment. All operators of the production equipment will be made aware as appropriate if the AI system is operational and if any automated actions are to be expected. If automated actions are expected, these will be restricted purely to optimisation of production parameters. The AI will be solely based on industrial production data, and there will be collection or use of any kind of personal data of any kind.

The application of AI within VITAL:

- Will not lead to potential stigmatisation or discrimination against people;
- Will not replace any decision-making processes that have a direct impact on human life, well-being or human rights;
- Will not lead to any negative social impacts.

4. Ethical advisor (EAd)

EAd (Ethical advisor) will monitor the ethics issues involved and how they are handled. EAd will attend project meetings when necessary and will be consulted on all ethical issues. VTT has proposed an EAd for the project. This person is PhD Marcin Waligora, Associate Professor and Vice Dean in REMEDY, Research Ethics in Medicine Study Group, Faculty of Health Science, Jagiellonian University Medical College, Krakow, Poland. More details: <https://bioetyka.wnz.cm.uj.edu.pl/en/people/dr-hab-marcin-waligora/> He was an ethics advisor in EU projects A-Patch and VOGAS, currently he is responsible for ethics in CARTHAGO EU funded project. He also serves as a member of the Rector's Ethics Committee at Jagiellonian University Medical College in Krakow.

5. Environment, health and safety

Experimental work may include elements that require attention to safety in order to ensure safe working conditions for research staff. If e.g. toxic chemicals are used, staff will be provided with adequate training in storing, handling and disposing of such substances.

It is of fundamental importance to VITAL that general principles concerning the prevention and protection of workers against occupational accidents and diseases are carefully assessed, and appropriate protective measures, as well as mitigation measures, are planned and implemented. The assessment covers aspects such as prevention of risks, the protection of safety and health, the assessment of risks, the elimination of risks and accident factors, the informing, consultation and balanced participation and training of workers and their representatives.

All partners are dedicated to the following principles to promote prevention:

- avoiding risks,
- evaluating the risks,
- combating the risks at the source,
- adapting the work to the individual,
- adapting to technical progress,
- replacing the dangerous with the non- or the less dangerous,
- developing a coherent overall prevention policy within the partners' organisation and VITAL project level,
- prioritizing collective protective measures (over individual protective measures),
- giving appropriate instructions to the workers.

The coordinator and the consortium partners will:

- Ensure that the working environment in the workplace complies with the requirements stated in the local/national guidelines/legislation.
- Safeguard the health and safety of all research participants.
- Ensure that all research participants in their organizations will acquire appropriate training for the execution of the lab work activities in VITAL.
- Follow the environmental regulations with respect to storage, transport, use and disposal of chemicals, according to Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS) documents.
- Ensure the wear of appropriate protective clothing and equipment (safety goggles, shoes, helmets and masks when required) and the installation of safety alarms and suitable detectors in workplaces where toxic and/or explosive gases can be emitted.
- Ensure that all working staff are well trained and educated about health and safety matters and procedures and ensure that junior employees will always have senior staff available to guide them.

VTT has established safety principles and procedures (described below). VTT as the coordinator requires that the project partners conducting experimental work implement similar safety principles while taking into account each organisation's own practices and instructions. Partners that have third parties, linked third parties, subcontracting or contracting are responsible for ensuring that they are compliant with the environment, health and safety guidelines.

VTT's safety principles and procedures

VTT requires a high level of safety in all its operations. Our objectives regarding occupational safety are the following:

- 1) The development and continuous improvement of occupational safety activities is part of our strategic planning.
- 2) VTT has the target of zero accidents.

3) Work at VTT is motivating and the individual's functional ability, resources and development needs are taken into account (physical, psychological and social loading).

4) It is safe and not damaging to health for people to work at VTT's facilities.

We ensure sufficient financial and human resources for taking care of the safety and support the competence development of the people responsible for the safety. Induction on safety is foreseen for all employees. VTT has a detailed guideline for safety at work and more detailed documents for specific hazardous workstations. We encourage the personnel to bring out all safety observations. We enhance our safety culture in a target-oriented systematic manner, considering the principles of continuous development. VTT's personnel has a duty to act according to the safety and security guidelines. The necessary safety and security processes are included in the contracts concluded with the cooperation partners. VTT's and its partners' personnel are obliged to inform their respective superior and VTT's Security Manager or Information Security Manager on any lack, threat or fault in safety and security.

VTT reports on corporate responsibility by applying the Global Reporting Initiative guidelines partly. VTT has been ISO14001-certified since 2014. VTT also reports on social responsibility issues according to the GRI Standards 2016. Relevant safety certificates beyond this link: <https://www.vttresearch.com/about-us/sustainable-development>

6. Conclusions

As part of the ethics management, the principles to underline the compliance of the project activities and tasks in the project with the specific ethic requirements concerning non-EU countries and artificial intelligence have been set in this report for the VITAL project.

The VITAL consortium carries out the project activities in compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national laws, and has also developed its own guidelines, procedures and measures aiming to support the protection of ethical aspects of research.

Good ethical management and ethical compliance are important to ensure transparent, fair, quality and trustworthy research (research integrity) and research results/outputs of the project. Good environmental, health and safety management is essential to minimize any potential risks and implement the do no significant harm principle. The VITAL consortium is conscious of the importance of good ethical practices and requirements and is committed to complying with them.